

BOTANY

ANTIOXIDANT, ANTIMICROBIAL AND ANTIVIRAL PROPERTIES OF SOME PLANTS USED IN TRADITIONAL MEDICINE

Mammadova A.

Assistant of Pharmacy department, Azerbaijan State Agricultural University

Tagizada A.

Senior teacher of Pharmacy department, Azerbaijan State Agricultural University

Nagiyeva M.

Head of Pharmacy department, Azerbaijan State Agricultural University

Kazımzade H.

Assistant of Pharmacy department, Azerbaijan State Agricultural University

Quluyeva S.

Assistant of Pharmacy department, Azerbaijan State Agricultural University

Abstract

In recent years, there has been a growing trend towards the increased utilization of herbal materials over synthetic or chemical drugs due to the comparatively milder side effects associated with past antibiotics. The application of herbs can take the form of plant extracts or their active constituents. Moreover, a significant portion of the global population has historically relied on herbal materials, owing to their potent antimicrobial properties and fundamental advantages for primary healthcare. The focus of this paper is to underscore the antibacterial, antiviral, and antioxidant attributes inherent in herbal materials. Various herbal antimicrobial agents are delineated in this review, encompassing clove, portulaca, cinnamon, turmeric, ginger, thyme, pennyroyal, mint, fennel, chamomile, burdock, lemon balm, mallow, and garlic, all of which are succinctly summarized.

Keywords: antioxidant, antimicrobial, antiviral, medicinal plants, traditional medicine.

The utilization of botanical substances as therapeutic botanicals encompasses various botanical species. Numerous botanical substances exhibit medicinal properties, including antioxidant, anticancer, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, and antiviral effects. While antimicrobial agents serve as antibiotics to manage infections within the human body, they may induce adverse reactions, particularly by augmenting reactive oxygen species levels [1]. Botanical remedies play a fundamental role in addressing infections in certain developing nations. Diverse investigations have highlighted the role of various botanical remedies as reservoirs of multiple compounds, many of which demonstrate radical scavenging abilities and antimicrobial characteristics, thereby fortifying the human body against pathogens and oxidative processes. Conse-

quently, these substances play a crucial role in formulating various botanical treatments due to their antimicrobial, antiviral, and antioxidant capabilities [2, 3, 4]. An antimicrobial agent or medicine is defined as a substance that can eradicate microorganisms or impede their proliferation. The classification of antimicrobial medications is based on their target microorganisms, such as bacteria and viruses.

Botanical antimicrobial agents, for instance, clove, portulaca, cinnamon, turmeric, ginger, thyme, pennyroyal, mint, fennel, chamomile, burdock, lemon balm, mallows, and garlic, possess the ability to function as scavengers of free radicals, thereby obstructing reactive oxygen species generation. The list of vital botanical substances with their primary components is presented in **Table 1**.

Table 1.

The list of herbal medicinal herbs

Medicinal plants	Main compounds
Clove	Eugenol, eugenyl acetate, α -humulene, and β -caryophyllene, 2-heptanone,
Portulaca	Ascorbic acid, a-tocopherols, omega-3 fatty acids, apigenin, gallotannins, quercetin, and kaempferol
Cinnamon	Cinnamaldehyde and eugenol
Turmeric	Vitamin-C, cineole, tumerone, borneol, zingiberene, d-sabinene and d-phellandrene
Ginger	Phenolic acids, gingerols, paradols and shogaols
Thyme	Carvacrol, thymol and phenols
Fennel	Phenolic compounds
Pennyrile	Neo-menthol, pulegone and menthone
Chamomile	Flavonoids, terpenoids, phenolic compounds, apigenin and matricin
Mint	Phenolic compounds
Burdock	Caffeic acid, rutin, o-hydrobenzoic acid, chlorogenic acid and p-coumaric acid
Lemon balm	Phenolic compounds such as thymol and carvacrol
Garlic	Organosulfur such as allicin, phenolic and polysaccharides compounds
Malva	β -carotene, flavonoids, vitamin E, polyphenols and vitamin C

Clove or *Syzygium aromaticum*, belonging to the Myrtaceae family, is renowned for its notable antimicrobial and antioxidant characteristics. By virtue of its bioactive constituents such as eugenol, eugenyl acetate, α -humulene, 2-heptanone, and β -caryophyllene, clove exhibits a wide array of pharmacological properties encompassing antimicrobial, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antimutagenic, anticancer, and anti-allergic effects. The presence of these bioactive elements endows clove with a remarkable antioxidant capacity, surpassing that of many other herbal remedies. Previous research has highlighted the substantial antibacterial efficacy of clove oil and extract against various bacterial strains, including both Gram-positive and Gram-negative types. Particularly, clove, through the action of eugenol, exerts antimicrobial effects. Furthermore, a study has demonstrated the antioxidant prowess of eugenol in clove extract against DPPH, ABTS, and superoxide radicals [6].

Portulaca oleracea is a traditional herb renowned for its remarkable antimicrobial and antioxidant properties. The predominant biomedicine activity of this plant stems from its potent antioxidant effects. These effects are predominantly attributed to various components found in portulaca, such as ascorbic acid, a-tocopherols, omega-3 fatty acids, apigenin, gallotannins, quercetin, and kaempferol. Omega-3 fatty acids, in particular, play a key role in the antioxidant activity of portulaca. Numerous studies have demonstrated the efficacy of this plant in combating various bacteria and fungi, underscoring its antimicrobial effects. The antioxidant and antimicrobial prowess of this medicinal herb can be attributed to its chemical composition, which includes phenolic compounds [5, 7].

Cinnamomum verum and *Cinnamomum zeylanicum*, is a member of the Lauraceae family. Due to its antioxidant, antimicrobial, and anticarcinogenic properties, it finds extensive application in pharmaceutical sectors. The traditional usage of cinnamon revolves around its antiseptic, antioxidant, and antimicrobial characteristics. The presence of phenolic compounds in

cinnamon contributes to its potential antioxidant, antimutagenic, antidiabetic, anticancer, and anti-inflammatory attributes. The essential oil derived from this plant has demonstrated notable antioxidant properties. Furthermore, investigations have highlighted the antioxidant potentials of water, methanol, and ethanolic extracts of cinnamon. Notably, this plant exhibits significant anti-influenza virus activity [8, 9].

Curcuma longa is a botanical remedy traditionally utilized, belonging to the *Zingiberaceae* family. The presence of curcumin, a polyphenolic compound, in turmeric extracts has exhibited both antimicrobial and antioxidant properties. As a result, the antioxidant capabilities of turmeric can be attributed to the phenolic compound curcumin. Turmeric contains various phytochemical structures such as vitamin C, cineole, tumerone, borneol, zingiberene, d-sabinene, and d-phellandrene. Within turmeric, a variety of chemical compounds are identified, including sesquiterpene ketones, monoterpenes, and sesquiterpene alcohols. Zingiberene is found in fresh turmeric, with curcumin being the most prominent curcuminoid in this plant. Past studies have documented the antimicrobial effects of turmeric. Research indicates the antiviral potential of turmeric against the HIV virus [10].

Ginger, which is the underground rhizome of *Zingiber officinale* roscoe and herbaceous perennial plants, is considered a fundamental herbal medicinal plant within the *Zingiberaceae* family. Originating in Asia, ginger has been utilized for medicinal purposes for over two millennia globally. It boasts polyphenol components, such as phenolic acids, gingerols, paradols, and shogaols, which play a crucial role in various biological activities including antioxidant, antidiabetic, antimicrobial, renoprotective, antihypertensive, antiulcer, anti-inflammatory, cardiovascular, analgesic, and gastrointestinal effects. The antioxidant properties of ginger are attributed to its chemical compounds like zingiberene, zingerone, shogaols, and gingerols. Numerous in vivo and in vitro laboratory experiments have inves-

tigated the antioxidant activities of ginger and its constituents, with some studies highlighting the potential antioxidant effects of ginger extract. Research on rats has specifically shown the antioxidant impact of ginger extract. Furthermore, studies have evidenced the antiviral efficacy of ginger against the influenza virus [11, 12].

Thymus vulgaris is considered one of the active antimicrobial herbal medicinal plants within the Lamiaceae family. This robust antimicrobial potency can be attributed to the substantial concentrations of carvacrol, thymol, and phenols present in thyme extracts and essential oils. Thyme extracts and essential oil exhibit a wide array of medicinal properties, encompassing antibacterial, antioxidant, antitussive, spasmolytic, anticancer and anti-inflammatory attributes. Traditionally, the extract from this plant has been utilized as an antitumor remedy due to its antioxidative characteristics [13].

Mentha pulegium represents one of the fragrant botanicals affiliated with the Lamiaceae family. The herb has been traditionally utilized in medicine for various purposes including skincare, aromatherapy and cosmetic applications due to its notable antioxidant and antimicrobial properties. Recent studies have shed light on the antioxidant characteristics of pennyroyal extracts and essential oils, emphasizing the chemical composition of this botanical specimen. The key bioactive elements found in pennyroyal extracts and essential oils are phenols, while its antimicrobial efficacy can be attributed to the presence of neo-menthol, pulegone, and menthone. Notably, this herbal remedy exhibits potent inhibitory effects against herpes virus and influenza virus [14].

Foeniculum vulgare is a member of the Apiaceae family. Various research endeavors have been conducted to investigate the radical scavenging capabilities of fennel, shedding light on its antioxidant properties. These investigations have elucidated that the high phenolic content present in fennel extracts contributes significantly to its antioxidant capacity. The efficacy of fennel in terms of antioxidant activity has been well-documented, with its extract being attributed to a multitude of antioxidant mechanisms including free radical scavenging, superoxide anion radical scavenging, total antioxidant, and hydrogen peroxide scavenging. As a result, fennel extracts and essential oils have the potential to serve as valuable natural sources for the development of innovative antimicrobial agents. Notably, fennel has exhibited inhibitory effects against the influenza A virus, further highlighting its pharmacological potential [15].

Chamomile, scientifically known as *Matricaria chamomilla*, represents a conventional form of botanical remedies. Belonging to the plant family Asteraceae, Chamomile continues to find applications in diverse sectors of the medical field, including pharmaceutical and cosmetic industries. The potent antimicrobial and antioxidant capabilities attributed to Chamomile can be primarily linked to the presence of flavonoids within its extract. Various pharmacological activities have been observed in Chamomile, encompassing antioxidative, antibacterial, anti-inflammatory, antifungal, analgesic,

anticancer, anti-hypoglycemic, anti-stress, antihypertensive, and hepatoprotective properties [16].

Mentha piperitha, is a perennial herb from the Lamiaceae family that is renowned for its aromatic properties. Its diverse uses encompass pharmaceuticals and cosmetics applications. Studies have demonstrated that mint essential oil can serve as a valuable short-term remedy for irritable bowel syndrome in individuals, attributed to its anti-inflammatory properties. Furthermore, this natural remedy exhibits inhibitory effects against HSV-1 and HIV viruses [17, 18].

Arctium lappa or burdock is a widely used traditional medicinal plant belonging to the Asteraceae family. Due to its phenolic rich compounds, burdock exhibits antimicrobial and antioxidant properties, along with other biochemical activities such as antipyresis and detoxification. Consequently, this plant can serve as an antioxidant, antimicrobial, and anti-inflammatory agent. Research has highlighted the antioxidant potential of burdock. Generally, burdock extracts have shown significant antimicrobial and antioxidant activities. These properties are attributed to the combined effects of caffeic acid, rutin, o-hydroxybenzoic acid, chlorogenic acid, and p-coumaric acid found in the extracts. Burdock leaves, in particular, display strong antimicrobial activity [19].

Lemon balm or *Melissa officinalis* is a traditional herbal medicine from the Lamiaceae family. The extracts and essential oils of lemon balm possess various pharmacological effects, including antimicrobial, anticancer, antibacterial, cardiovascular protection, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antispasmodic, and antiviral properties. Rich in phenolic compounds such as thymol and carvacrol, lemon balm's antibacterial and antioxidant activities are notable [20].

Malva sylvestris a medicinal herb belonging to the Malvaceae family. This plant's extract is rich in phenolic content and has notable antimicrobial properties. Over the past decade, mallow extract has been applied medicinally due to its beneficial effects on various bodily systems, including the skin, muscular and skeletal systems, and respiratory and digestive systems. Mallow exhibits spasmolytic, lenitive, laxative, diuretic, demulcent, anti-diarrheal, bronchodilator, expectorant, and antitussive properties. Its high antimicrobial and antioxidant activities make it particularly recommended for skincare. These properties are linked to its chemical constituents, such as β -carotene, flavonoids, vitamin E, polyphenols, and vitamin C. The primary reason for mallow's excellent antioxidant and antimicrobial capabilities is its polyphenol content. Consequently, both alcoholic and aqueous extracts of mallow exhibit pharmacological effects, including antiviral, anti-inflammatory, antibacterial, and anti-carcinogenic properties [21].

Allium sativum an herbal medicine from the *Amaryllidaceae* family. Garlic is known for its biological activities, including antioxidant, immunomodulatory, antidiabetic, anticancer, antibacterial, cardioprotective, and anti-inflammatory effects. Its major components include phenolic compounds, polysaccharides, and organosulfur compounds, along with saponins, amino acids, flavonoids, vitamins A and C, B-complex vitamins,

and minerals. As a natural antioxidant, garlic helps inhibit the harmful effects of free radicals in cells. It is recognized for its antimicrobial and antioxidant characteristics in traditional medicine. The antioxidant properties of garlic are attributed to its chemical components, including organosulfur and phenolic compounds. Amino acids like alliin are significant components of garlic. The enzyme alliinase converts alliin into allicin, a key component responsible for garlic's antimicrobial activity [22].

Numerous researchers have highlighted the biomedical uses of herbal medicines. While antibiotics and other chemical antimicrobial agents, including metal oxides and nanoparticles, can inhibit bacterial growth, they often generate reactive oxygen species and other side effects. In contrast, herbal medicines like clove, portulaca, cinnamon, turmeric, ginger, thyme, pennyroyal, mint, fennel, chamomile, burdock, lemon balm, mallow, and garlic can eliminate bacteria by acting as free radical scavengers. The antibacterial efficacy of these herbs varies across different bacteria and depends on the type of extract or essential oil used. Some studies have explored the advantages and limitations of nanofibrous dressings, which have a large surface area and can locally release antibiotics, herbal medicines, and antibacterial agents to treat infections. The phenolic compounds in the extracts or essential oils of these herbs typically exhibit strong antioxidant and antimicrobial properties. Therefore, herbal medicines are often preferred over synthetic antimicrobial agents due to their lower toxicity and fewer side effects. Given their potent antimicrobial and antioxidant properties, these herbs can aid in healing various types of wounds.

Bioavailability is a crucial factor in assessing the health benefits of herbal medicines for humans. This paper thoroughly discusses the antioxidant, antimicrobial, and antiviral properties of individual herbs. The use of herb combinations is also common in traditional medicine. Future research should focus on identifying active components and studying the effects of herb-herb combinations for therapeutic advancements and pharmaceutical development.

References

1. Shaikh S., Nazam N., Rizvi SM D., Ahmad K., Baig M.H., Lee E.J., Choi I. Mechanistic insights into the antimicrobial actions of metallic nanoparticles and their implications for multidrug resistance. *Int. J. Mol. Sci.* 2019;20:2468.
2. Saratale, R.G.; Benelli, G.; Kumar, G.; Kim, D.S.; Saratale, G.D. Bio-fabrication of silver nanoparticles using the leaf extract of an ancient herbal medicine, dandelion (*Taraxacum officinale*), evaluation of their antioxidant, anticancer potential, and antimicrobial activity against phytopathogens. *Environ. Sci. Pollut. R.* 2018, 25, 10392–10406.
3. Miraj, S.; Rafieian-Kopaei, M.; Kiani, S. *Melissa officinalis* L.: A review study with an antioxidant prospective. *Evid. Based Complement. Alternat Med.* 2017, 22, 385–394.
4. Sharma, A.; del Carmen Flores-Vallejo, R.; Cardoso-Taketa, A.; Villarreal, M.L. Antibacterial activities of medicinal plants used in Mexican traditional medicine. *J. Ethnopharmacol.* 2017, 208, 264–329.
5. Zhou Y.X., Xin H.L., Rahman K., Wang S.J., Peng C., Zhang H. *Portulaca oleracea* L.: A review of phytochemistry and pharmacological effects. *Bio. Med. Res. Int.* 2015;2015:925631.
6. Radünz M., da Trindade M.L., Camargo T.M., Radünz A.L., Borges C.D., Gandra E.A., Helbig E. Antimicrobial and antioxidant activity of unencapsulated and encapsulated clove (*Syzygium aromaticum*, L.) essential oil. *Food Chem.* 2019;276:180–186.
7. Jaiswal S., Rajwade D. A Review on *Portulaca oleracea* (Nonia bhaji): A wonderful weed of Chhattisgarh. *Res. J. Pharm Technol.* 2017;10:2415–2420.
8. Chuesiang P., Siripatrawan U., Sanguandeeikul R., McClements D.J., McLandsborough L. Antimicrobial activity of PIT-fabricated cinnamon oil nanoemulsions: Effect of surfactant concentration on morphology of foodborne pathogens. *Food Control.* 2019;98:405–411.
9. Gulcin I., Kaya R., Goren A.C., Akincioglu H., Topal M., Bingol Z., Cetin Ç.K., Ozturk S.S.B., Durmaz L., Alwasel S. Anticholinergic, antidiabetic and antioxidant activities of cinnamon (*cinnamomum verum*) bark extracts: Polyphenol contents analysis by LC-MS/MS. *Int. J. Food Prop.* 2019;22:1511–1526.
10. Sharma, S.; Ghataury, S.K.; Sarathe, A.; Dubey, G.; Parkhe, G. *Curcuma angustifolia* Roxb, (Zingiberaceae): Ethnobotany, phytochemistry and pharmacology: A review. *J. Pharmacogn. Phytochem.* 2019, 8, 1535–1540.
11. Idris, N.A.; Yasin, H.M.; Usman, A. Voltammetric and spectroscopic determination of polyphenols and antioxidants in ginger (*Zingiber officinale* Roscoe). *Heliyon* 2019, 5, e01717.
12. Wang, X.; Shen, Y.; Thakur, K.; Han, J.; Zhang, J.G.; Hu, F.; Wei, Z.J. Antibacterial activity and mechanism of ginger essential oil against *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus*. *Molecules* 2020, 25, 3955.
13. Benameur, Q.; Gervasi, T.; Pellizzeri, V.; Pl'uchtová, M.; Tali-Maama, H.; Assaous, F.; Guettou, B.; Rahal, K.; Grul'ová, D.; Dugo, G.; et al. Antibacterial activity of *Thymus vulgaris* essential oil alone and in combination with cefotaxime against bla ESBL producing multidrug resistant Enterobacteriaceae isolates. *Nat. Prod. Res.* 2019, 33, 2647–2654.
14. Gheisari, Z.; Kalani, L.; Khaledi, M.; Nouri, A.; Eshaghi Milasi, Y.; Hossainy, N.; Soleymani, A. Antibacterial Effects of Hydro-alcoholic Extract of Pennyroyal, Cinnamon and Rhubarb on *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and *Staphylococcus aureus*: An In vitro Study. *J. Pharm. Res. Inter.* 2019, 17, 1–6.
15. Bettaieb ép Rebey, I.; Bourgou, S.; Marzouk, B.; Fauconnier, M.L.; Ksouri, R. Salinity impact on seed yield, polyphenols composition and antioxidant activity of Fennel (*Foeniculum vulgare* Mill) extracts. *J. New Sci.* 2017, 2017, 2610–2619.
16. Agatonovic-Kustrin, S.; Ortakand, D.B.; Morton, D.W.; Yusof, A.P. Rapid evaluation and compari-

son of natural products and antioxidant activity in calendula, feverfew, and German chamomile extracts. *J. Chromatogr. A* 2015, 1385, 103–110.

17. Vaghardoost, R.; Ghavami, Y.; Sobouti, B. The effect of *Mentha Pulegium* on healing of burn wound injuries in rat. *World J. Plast Surg.* 2019, 8, 43.

18. Salem, N.; Sriti, J.; Bachrouch, O.; Msaada, K.; Khammassi, S.; Hammami, M. Phenological stage effect on phenolic composition and repellent potential of *Mentha pulegium* against *Tribolium castaneum* and *Lasioderma serricornis*. *Asian Pac. J. Trop Biomed.* 2018, 8, 207.

19. Fierascu, R.C.; Georgiev, M.I.; Fierascu, I.; Ungureanu, C.; Avramescu, S.M.; Ortan, A.; Georgescu, M.I.; Sutan, A.N.; Zangfirescu, A.; Dinu-Pirvu, C.E.; et al. Mitodepressive, antioxidant, antifungal and anti-inflammatory effects of wild-growing Ro-

manian native *Arctium lappa* L.(Asteraceae) and *Veronica persica* Poiret (Plantaginaceae). *Food Chem. Toxicol.* 2018, 111, 44–52.

20. Pirbalouti, A.G.; Nekoei, M.; Rahimmalek, M.; Malekpoor, F. Chemical composition and yield of essential oil from lemon balm (*Melissa officinalis* L.) under foliar applications of jasmonic and salicylic acids. *Biocatal. Agric. Biotechnol.* 2019, 19, 101144.

21. Sharifi-Rad, J.; Melgar-Lalanne, G.; Hernández-Álvarez, A.J.; Taheri, Y.; Shaheen, S.; Kregiel, D.; Antolak, H.; Pawlikowska, E.; Brdar-Jokanović, M.; Rajkovic, J.; et al. Malva species: Insights on its chemical composition towards pharmacological applications. *Phytother. Res.* 2020, 34, 546–567.

22. Divya, B.J.; Suman, B.; Venkataswamy, M.; Thyagaraju, K. A study on phytochemicals, functional groups and mineral composition of *Allium sativum* (garlic) cloves. *Int. J. Curr. Pharm. Res.* 2017, 9, 42–45.